

TEXT TALK: A STRATEGY IN ENHANCING VOCABULARY SKILLS OF GRADE III LEARNERS

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Text Talk: A Strategy in Enhancing Vocabulary Skills of Grade III Learners

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Text Talk strategy in teaching vocabulary of Grade III learners of Kabacsanan Elementary School, Iligan City, SY 2023-2024. A pretest and a posttest design were used. The study employed one group pretest posttest research design and made use of a questionnaire in gathering data. Results revealed that the analysis of the differences between the pretest and posttest scores of the participants demonstrated a remarkable and highly significant improvement in their performance. The mean pretest score of 9.90 increased substantially to 13.67 in the posttest, showcasing a significant positive change. The paired t-test, with a highly significant t-value of -19.837 (df=29) and a p-value of 0.000 ($p < .001$), confirmed that this improvement was not a result of chance but rather a direct outcome of the effectiveness of the intervention or program being assessed. Thus, the analysis explored the connection between learners' vocabulary scores and their attitudes toward the Text Talk strategy intervention. In this context, the "not significant" remark indicates that the relationship between vocabulary scores and attitude toward the intervention is not statistically significant, as the p-value exceeds the conventional significance level of 0.05. This implied that learners' vocabulary proficiency does not have a significant influence on their attitude toward the Text Talk strategy.

Keywords: *text talk, strategy, vocabulary, quasi-experimental*

Introduction

Understanding vocabulary serves as a foundation of prior knowledge, enriching the comprehension of reading. Students facing challenges in comprehension often struggle to acquire new vocabulary, as their tendency to read less hinders the application of new meanings to unfamiliar words. Consequently, a growing disparity emerges between them and their more accomplished peers, leading to increasingly evident reading difficulties in later grades.

However, the researcher would like to introduce another vocabulary instruction that can be achieved by the incorporation of an intervention framework that balances the teaching of word-learning strategies fostering whole-story integration. As mandated in DepEd Memorandum 14, S. 2018 – Policy Guidelines on the administration of the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory, every school has to conduct Phil-IRI. The result of Phil-IRI serves as basis for planning, designing/redesigning the reading instruction of the teachers and the school's reading programs or activities to improve the overall school's reading performance.

The result of Phil-IRI in Kabacsanan Elementary School, North I District, showed that the learners have poor vocabulary skills where 56% frustration for girls and 59% frustration for boys. The result implied that the learners cannot understand the text read because of their poor vocabulary skills. As one of the English components, vocabulary is very important to learn. Before the students master the four skills, they must know some vocabulary to support them in learning English. English vocabulary as one of the language skill elements has an important role for young learners in learning foreign languages (Syafrietal et.,al 2018). In presenting English, especially vocabulary, the teacher should be creative in choosing materials and able to stimulate the student's interest. The teacher needs to manipulate some strategies to support the teaching and learning process. Teaching English to young learners is different from teaching adults in a way that they are often more enthusiastic, active, and easily adaptive than adults.

Moreover, vocabulary is considered a core aspect of language and is a key marker of overall verbal language development and verbal intelligence, with typical school children learning 10–20 new words each day. Vocabulary encompasses both the words an individual can understand (receptive vocabulary) and the words they can produce and use (expressive vocabulary). In childhood, vocabulary is typically assess via visual tasks (i.e., picture naming or matching a spoken word to a picture), and predominately considers knowledge of concrete nouns and verbs. Whilst a range of psychosocial factors are known to influence verbal language and vocabulary development (e.g., male gender, parent-child interactions, and maternal education, vocabulary, and mental health; the cognitive skills and underlying brain mechanisms that contribute to vocabulary development remain largely undefined (Samuelson, 2021).

The main objective of the study was to determine the effectiveness of Text Talk strategy, as a proactive intervention to enhance learners' vocabulary development. The study was conducted in the first quarter of the SY: 2023-2024 to the grade III learners of Kabacsanan Elementary School, North 1 district, Iligan City. The researcher is in 6 years of service and has been teaching grade III for almost three years. It is her desire to use effective vocabulary strategies to help educate children as they learn new words. Also, the researcher wanted to have fulfilment in her career in which she can contribute to the attainment of quality learning by improving the vocabulary skills of learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the contribution of Text Talk strategy to enhance the vocabulary development of Grade III learners of

Kabacsanan Elementary School, North I District, Division of Iligan City for SY 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the pretest scores of respondents?
2. What are the posttest scores of respondents?
3. What is the gain scores of the pretest and posttest groups?
4. What is the attitude of the learners toward the text talk strategy?
5. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and the posttest scores of the respondents?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the vocabulary scores of learners and their attitudes towards the intervention Text talk strategy?
7. What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used one group pretest - posttest experimental research design. The basic premise behind the pretest-posttest design involves giving a pretest measurement before administering some treatment, followed by a posttest on the same measurement after treatment occurs (Reichardt, 2019). This design was used to compare participants and measure the degree of change occurring as a result of the treatment.

Participants

The participants of the study were the grade three learners for whom the researcher taught at Kabacsanan Elementary School. Since the researcher taught all of the subjects in the said section, the advantage of accessing their performance rating was easy. It further made the conduct of research easier since the number of learners in the group was very manageable. There were 15 males and 15 females as of this school year. A complete enumeration of the participants was employed in the study.

Instruments

The research instrument was a teacher-made questionnaire. Contents of the pretest and posttest were the English vocabulary competencies as required by the K to 12 English Curriculum for Grade III. The stories were acquired from the Summer Big Brother Module given by the (CLAFI) Conrado and Ladislawa Alcantara Foundation. The type of test was a multiple choice composed of 20 items. Every question had four options for an accurate response. Six items for the competency, Review reading and writing short e, a, i, o, and u words in CVC pattern EN3PWR-Ia-b-7, eight items for the competency, read phrases, sentences and short stories consisting of 2-syllable words EN3PWR-Ij-21 and seven items for the competency, read words with initial and final consonant blends EN3PWR-IIi-j-22.1. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for correction before it was validated by the master teachers of Iligan City North I Central School, North III District and after, it was pilot tested to the 30 grade 3 learners in the same school.

To ensure the validity of the research instrument, the questionnaire underwent pilot testing at North I Central School. The reliability statistics result showed some items to be discarded and some items also to be revised. The discrimination index (DI) measures how discriminating items in an exam are – i.e. how well an item can differentiate between good candidates and less able ones. For each item, it is a measure based on the comparison of performance between stronger and weaker items in the exam as a whole. The discrimination index value for an item ranges from -1 to +1 with positive numbers over 0.2 reliably implying that an item is positively discriminating.

Thus, the instrument used in this study has at least acceptable internal consistency, indicating that it can be used for future research purposes.

In the scoring procedure, the data gathered are analyzed and interpreted as follows:

Discrimination Index (DI) of each item				
Item Number	GROUP		DISCRIMINATION INDEX	
	Upper (U)	Lower (L)	DI	INTERPRETATION
1	10	8	0.2	moderately discriminating
2	10	8	0.2	moderately discriminating
3	10	5	0.5	discriminating
4	10	5	0.5	discriminating
5	10	7	0.3	discriminating
6	10	8	0.2	moderately discriminating
7	8	4	0.4	discriminating
8	10	2	0.8	very discriminating
9	10	7	0.3	discriminating
10	8	4	0.4	discriminating
11	10	7	0.3	discriminating

12	2	2	0	moderately discriminating
13	10	3	0.7	very discriminating
14	10	8	0.2	moderately discriminating
15	0	6	-0.6	questionable item
16	10	7	0.3	discriminating
17	8	4	0.4	discriminating
18	0	0	0	moderately discriminating
19	9	8	0.1	moderately discriminating
20	10	7	0.3	discriminating

Action Based on Difficulty and Discriminating Level of an Item

Item Number	Difficulty Index	Discrimination Index	Action
1	very easy item	moderately discriminating	may need revision
2	very easy item	moderately discriminating	may need revision
3	easy item	discriminating	accept
4	easy item	discriminating	accept
5	very easy item	discriminating	accept
6	very easy item	moderately discriminating	may need revision
7	moderately difficult	discriminating	accept
8	moderately difficult	very discriminating	accept
9	very easy item	discriminating	accept
10	moderately difficult	discriminating	accept
11	very easy item	discriminating	accept
12	difficult item	moderately discriminating	may need revision
13	easy item	very discriminating	accept
14	very easy item	moderately discriminating	may need revision
15	difficult item	questionable item	replace/discard
16	very easy item	discriminating	accept
17	moderately difficult	discriminating	accept
18	very difficult item	moderately discriminating	may need revision
19	very easy item	moderately discriminating	may need revision
20	very easy item	discriminating	accept

Range of Difficulty (D) Interpretation				Range of Index of Discrimination Interpretation			
0	to	0.2	Very Difficult Item	-1	to	-0.6	Questionable item
0.21	to	0.4	Difficult Item	-0.59	to	-0.2	Not Discriminating
0.41	to	0.6	Moderately Difficult	0.19	to	0.2	Moderately Discriminating
0.61	to	0.8	Easy Item	0.21	to	0.6	Discriminating
0.81	to	1	Very Easy Item	0.61	to	1	Very Discriminating

Procedure

The researcher personally conducted the study and facilitated the gathering of data. The data-gathering process was done in this manner: After complying with the protocols in asking permission to conduct the study, the researcher proceeded to conduct the study with the respondents. The pretest was conducted during the first quarter of the SY: 2023-2024 to assess the participants' knowledge before applying the treatment (Text-Talk integration). Following the pretest, the implementation of the Text Talk strategy commenced. The teacher read sentences from the story containing the target word, prompting learners to repeat the word. The teacher proceeded to explain the word's meaning and offered examples beyond those used in the story. Learners were then encouraged to provide their own examples. Finally, they were asked to reiterate the word.

After a month of teaching vocabulary development, a posttest with similar contents to the pretest was administered to measure the participants' knowledge achievement after the treatment's application. Although the test items in the pretest and posttest were the same, the test items were shuffled in the posttest. The results were collated and submitted to the accredited statistician of the school.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were utilized to analyze and explain the variation in the sample data.

For Problems 1 & 2- Frequency and Percentage were used to determine the distribution of the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents with the use of text talk strategy.

For Problems 3 & 4- Mean and Standard deviation (SD) was used to describe the average and deviation of the scores of the respondents as well as their attitude level on the use of text talk strategy.

For Problem 5- Paired T –test was used to determine the paired differences between the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents.

For Problem 6- Pearson r Correlation- was used to determine the relationship between the attitudes and the post-test scores of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the analyses, results, and discussions of the data gathered by the researcher.

PROBLEM 1: What are the pretest scores of the participants?

Table 1. *Pretest Scores of the Participants*

<i>Pretest Scores</i>	<i>Performance Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
19-20	Outstanding	0	0
16-18	Very Satisfactory	3	10.0
13-15	Satisfactory	5	17.0
10-12	Fairly Satisfactory	9	30.0
0-9	Did not meet expectations	13	43.0
Total		30	100.0

Table 1 presents the pretest scores of the participants and their corresponding performance levels in the pre-assessment. It is evident that none of the participants achieved an outstanding performance in the pretest, which accounts for 0% of the total. However, the majority of the participants fell into the lower performance categories. Specifically, 10% of the participants achieved a very satisfactory performance, while 17% reached a satisfactory level. A substantial portion, 30%, scored at a fairly satisfactory level. Notably, the largest group, comprising 43% of the total, did not meet expectations, receiving a score of 0-9 in the pretest.

These findings carry significant implications for the evaluated study. The lack of exceptional performance scores implies that there might be opportunities for enhancement in the employed teaching or training methods. The fact that most participants landed in the lower performance brackets suggests a potential requirement for extra support and intervention to assist them in reaching higher levels of proficiency. The notable proportion of participants falling below expectations is worrisome, underscoring the need for focused interventions and program modifications to ensure that a greater number of individuals can attain satisfactory or superior performance levels.

PROBLEM 2: What are the posttest scores of the participants?

Table 2. *Posttest Scores of the Participants*

<i>Posttest Scores</i>	<i>Performance Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
19-20	Outstanding	0	0
16-18	Very Satisfactory	12	40.0
13-15	Satisfactory	7	23.0
10-12	Fairly Satisfactory	7	23.0
0-9	Did not meet expectations	4	13.0
Total		30	100.0

Table 2 shows the posttest scores of the participants, along with their corresponding performance levels following the assessment. No participant achieved an outstanding score in the posttest, representing 0% of the total. Conversely, the distribution of performance levels in the posttest has improved compared to the pretest. A significant portion, 40% of the participants, achieved a very satisfactory score, indicating substantial progress. Additionally, 23% attained satisfactory and another 23% scored at the fairly satisfactory level. A smaller percentage, 13%, still did not meet expectations, falling within the 0-9 score range in the posttest.

These results carry important implications for the assessment or program under evaluation. However, the significant increase in participants achieving very satisfactory performance in the posttest compared to the pretest suggests that the program or intervention has had a positive impact on a substantial portion of the participants. The fact that over 46% of the participants now fall into the satisfactory or fairly satisfactory categories is a promising sign of progress. Nevertheless, the 13% who still did not meet expectations signifies that there is room for further improvement to ensure that all participants can reach at least a satisfactory level. This result emphasizes the importance of continuous evaluation and adaptation in educational or training programs to maximize the effectiveness of interventions and improve overall outcomes.

According to Arden (2022), vocabulary skills is critical to each student's academic achievement. Efficient vocabulary strategies support children in acquiring new words. Moreover, the Text Talk strategy may assist learners in improving their vocabulary skills.

Implementing the text talk strategy in this way may enhance learners' vocabulary skills for improved comprehension. Initially, the teacher clarifies the word's meaning, offers examples, and then guides learners as they contribute their examples.

PROBLEM 3: What is the gain score of the pretest and posttest groups?

Table 3. *Gain Scores of the Participants*

<i>Gain Scores</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
5	9	30.0
4	9	30.0
3	8	27.0
2	4	13.0
Total	30	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 3.77 (1.04)

Table 3 presents the gain scores of the participants, reflecting the difference between their posttest and pretest scores. The majority of participants demonstrated positive gains, with 30% achieving a gain score of 5 and another 30% achieving a gain score of 4. An additional 27% had gain scores of 3, while 13% had gain scores of 2. The total sample of 30 participants achieved a mean gain score of 3.77, with a standard deviation of 1.04.

These gain scores offer valuable insights into the overall progress of the participants. The fact that the majority of participants showed gain scores of 4 or 5 is a positive indicator, suggesting that the program or intervention had a substantial impact on their performance. The mean gain score of 3.77 also reflects an overall improvement, indicating that, on average, participants experienced positive growth from the pretest to the posttest. However, it is important to recognize the variation in gain scores, as some participants achieved smaller gains (2 or 3) and a small percentage even demonstrated a decline in performance. This variation underscores the need for a more detailed analysis to identify the factors contributing to individual differences in gain scores and to tailor support and interventions accordingly.

Overall, these results highlight the effectiveness of the program but also indicate the importance of continued efforts to support and enhance the learning experiences of participants. Moody et al. (2018) clarified in their article that a well-developed vocabulary has long been recognized as essential for success in reading, and literature has repeatedly affirmed that vocabulary size is one of the strongest predictors of reading development.

Problem 4: What is the attitude of the learners toward the text talk strategy?

Table 4. *Attitude of the Learners toward the Text talk Strategy*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I like to use the strategy Text Talk.	3.97	0.18	Strongly Agree
2. I feel like I can easily find the answer through Text Talk.	3.27	0.45	Agree
3. I enjoy writing the answers in the box provided.	3.67	0.48	Strongly Agree
4. Text Talk strategy help me to understand the story read.	3.90	0.31	Strongly Agree
5. I can easily think of an answer through Text Talk.	3.43	0.50	Agree
6. I can read with comprehension through Text Talk.	3.40	0.50	Agree
7. I can easily retell the story through Text Talk.	3.50	0.51	Strongly Agree
8. I am excited to answer the comprehension questions through Text Talk.	3.73	0.45	Strongly Agree
9. I can easily memorize the meaning of the difficult words in the story using Text Talk.	3.33	0.48	Agree
10. The Text Talk strategy inspires me to better understand the challenging words in the story I'm reading.	3.67	0.48	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.59	0.25	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 4 displays the participants' attitudes toward the Text Talk strategy, presenting their mean scores and standard deviations (SD) for each indicator. The mean for the total measure is 3.59, falling within the "Strongly Agree" range, indicating that, on the average, learners held a highly positive attitude toward the Text Talk strategy. Additionally, the low standard deviation of 0.25 suggests that the responses were relatively consistent among the participants.

Examining each indicator in detail, the result found that learners expressed strong agreement (mean scores ranging from 3.90 to 3.73) with statements such as "Text Talk strategy helps them understand the story read" and "they are excited to answer the comprehension questions through Text Talk." These high mean scores suggested that the Text-Talk strategy was well-received and perceived as highly effective in aiding comprehension and engagement.

While the mean scores for some indicators fell within the "Agree" range (3.27 to 3.50), such as "I feel like I can easily find the answer through Text Talk" and "I can read with comprehension through Text Talk," they still indicated a positive attitude. These scores suggested room for potential improvement in specific aspects of the strategy or room for tailored support in certain areas.

The overwhelmingly positive attitudes of learners towards the Text-Talk strategy are encouraging. It indicated that the strategy has been successful in engaging students and enhancing their comprehension and participation in reading activities. However, for the

indicators in the "Agree" range, it may be beneficial to explore ways to further strengthen these aspects of the strategy or provide additional support to address any challenges learners may face. Overall, the findings from this assessment suggested that the Text Talk strategy is a valuable tool for fostering positive attitudes and effective learning experiences among students.

As cited by Arden (2022), vocabulary skills that are critical to each student's academic achievement. In and out of the classroom, student success depends on grasping reading comprehension and English language development. Effective vocabulary strategies help educate children as they learn new words.

Problem 5: Is there a significant difference between the pretest and the posttest scores of the participants?

Table 5. Differences between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Participants

Paired Variable	Scores		t-value (df)	p-value	Remark
	Mean	SD			
Pretest	9.90	3.96	-19.837*** (29)	.000	Significant
Posttest	13.67	3.65			

Note: *** $p < .001$

Table 5 presents the differences between the pretest and posttest scores of the participants, along with associated statistical data. The mean pretest score is 9.90 with a standard deviation (SD) of 3.96, while the mean posttest score is 13.67 with an SD of 3.65. The paired t-test analysis revealed a highly significant t-value of -19.837 (df=29) and a p-value of .000, (denoted as $p < .001$), indicating a remarkable level of statistical significance.

These results suggested a substantial and positive change in the participants scores from the pretest to the posttest. The mean pretest score of 9.90 increased to 13.67 in the posttest, highlighting a significant improvement in their performance. The highly significant p-value ($p < .001$) indicated that this change is not due to chance and can be attributed to the effectiveness of the intervention or program being evaluated.

These results suggest that the considerable increase in scores from the pretest to the posttest signifies a substantial positive impact of the program or intervention on the participants' performance. It indicates that the program effectively played a role in improving their skills or knowledge. These findings underscore the significance of the intervention and emphasize the necessity of ongoing implementation or refinement to ensure sustained positive outcomes.

It also underscores the value of ongoing assessments to monitor progress and make necessary adjustments to optimize the learning experiences of the participants. The more relevant words the language learners know, the better for them. Susanto et al. (2019) clearly stated in their journal that vocabulary as well as grammar and pronunciation for all language learners, is one of the elements of language considered necessary for language mastery. Vocabulary is just as important as the main four skills of listening, reading, writing, and speaking.

Problem 6: Is there a significant relationship between the vocabulary scores of learners and their attitudes toward the intervention Text Talk strategy?

Table 6. Relationship between the Vocabulary Scores of Learners and their Attitude toward the Intervention Text Talk Strategy

Variable	Attitude toward the Intervention		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Vocabulary Scores	-.161	.396	Not significant

Note: not significant means $p\text{-value} > .05$

Table 6 presents the results of an analysis examining the relationship between the vocabulary scores of learners and their attitude toward the Text Talk strategy intervention. The analysis revealed an r-value of -.161 and a p-value of .396. In this context, a "not significant" remark means that the relationship between vocabulary scores and attitude toward the intervention is not statistically significant, as the p-value is greater than the conventional significance level of .05.

These findings imply that there isn't a statistically significant correlation between learners' vocabulary scores and their attitude toward the Text Talk strategy. Essentially, the learners' performance on vocabulary assessments does not seem to impact their attitudes toward this particular intervention. This outcome is promising, suggesting that the strategy is well-received regardless of learners' vocabulary proficiency. It indicates that the strategy's appeal and effectiveness are not dependent on learners' prior vocabulary skills, potentially ensuring that a diverse range of students can benefit from the intervention.

Problem 7: What Action Plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

The rationale for this school learning action plan is based on the findings of the study, which revealed both strengths and areas for improvement in the implementation of the Text Talk strategy. The action plan is designed to address these findings and to further enhance the learning experience for students systematically and comprehensively.

<i>Key Action Steps/ Strategies To Achieve Objective</i>	<i>Persons Responsible</i>	<i>Resources/ Budget Needed</i>	<i>Date Of Completion</i>	<i>Threats/Potential Barriers</i>	<i>Indicators Of Success</i>
Conduct orientation on the use of Text Talk strategy	School Head Researcher	Php 1,000.00/MOOE	July- August, 2024	Unavailability of time of the participants due to workloads and meeting their deadlines for the submission of reports	100% of the teachers attended the orientation
To demonstrate the use of text talk strategy in teaching vocabulary skills	School Head Master Teachers Teachers Researcher	Php 5,000.00/MOOE	July- August, 2024	Overlapping of activities in school	100% of the teachers attended the demo teaching
Monitor & collect feedback from learners about their experience toward the Text Talk Strategy	Teachers, Learners School Guidance	Php 1,000.00/MOOE	Every quarter	Lack of appropriate survey tools	100% of the learners answered the survey tools
Analyze feedback data and identify areas for improvement	School Head Master Teachers Teachers School Guidance	Php 1,000.00/MOOE	Quarterly	Lack of data analysis tools	100% chance in analyzing feedback data and identify areas for improvement
Conduct action research to determine the effectiveness of text talk strategy in teaching other discipline	Teachers	Php 5,000.00/MOOE	Annually	Unavailability of time of teachers due to workloads and meeting their deadlines for the submission of reports	100% of the teachers conducted action research
Conduct parents' orientation to understand their perspectives	Administrators, Teachers Parents	Php 1,000.00/MOOE	Quarterly	Not all parents/guardians attended the orientation	100% collaboration with parents and guardians to understand their perspectives

Conclusions

Based on the findings derived from the study, the following conclusions were formulated below:

First, the initial pretest assessment revealed that none of the participants achieved an outstanding performance level. The majority of participants fell into lower performance categories, with a significant portion not meeting expectations. Nonetheless, in the subsequent posttest, although no participants achieved an outstanding level, there was a noteworthy enhancement in performance. This indicates that the educational or training program exerted a positive influence on the participants, resulting in overall progress.

Second, the gain scores, which reflect the difference between posttest and pretest scores, showed that a significant majority of participants experienced positive gains, indicating that the intervention effectively enhanced their performance.

Third, the attitudes of learners toward the Text Talk strategy were overwhelmingly positive. This suggests that the strategy was well-received and perceived as highly effective in improving vocabulary skills and engagement among students.

Lastly, the analysis revealed no statistically significant relationship between learners' vocabulary scores and their attitudes toward the Text Talk strategy. This indicates that the strategy's appeal and effectiveness were consistent across learners with varying vocabulary skills.

Accordingly, this strategy allows learners to learn new vocabulary, memorize the meaning of the words being presented, and make connections between the concepts that lead to meaningful learning. Besides, because the Text Talk strategy is student-centered; they have more chances to work on reading outside the classroom context.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations were stipulated below:

Curriculum planners may consider the study's findings as a call for ongoing review and alignment of curriculum with effective strategies such as the Text Talk strategy. These findings suggest that the curriculum should be designed with flexibility to accommodate diverse learner needs, allowing for further customization. Curriculum planners should collaborate with educators to continuously adapt and refine curriculum materials to ensure they meet the needs of the students, addressing areas where performance is below the desired

level.

School administrators may use the study's conclusions to reinforce the importance of ongoing professional development for teachers. The findings underscore the positive impact of the educational program on student performance but also highlight areas where improvement is needed. Administrators may allocate resources to provide teachers with regular training, support, and opportunities for collaboration to enhance their effectiveness. Additionally, they may consider implementing data-driven decision-making processes to monitor student progress and tailor interventions accordingly.

Teachers may take these findings as a motivation to refine their teaching methods and strategies continuously. The positive gains and attitudes of students indicate that the strategies in place are effective but can be further improved. Teachers may collaborate and share best practices with colleagues and focus on personalized approaches to address the diverse learning needs within their classrooms. Furthermore, they may consider using student feedback to adapt their teaching methods and materials to maintain the high level of engagement and positive attitudes observed in the study.

For learners, these findings suggest the importance of active participation in their own learning process. The study indicates that the strategies in place are beneficial and can lead to substantial improvements. Learners may actively engage with the provided materials, express their preferences, and provide feedback to educators. This will ensure that their specific needs are considered and that their learning experience is optimized.

For future researchers, the study highlights several avenues for further investigation. Specifically, researchers could explore the effectiveness of the Text Talk strategy in different educational settings, with different age groups, or in various subject areas.

The action plan as an output of the study be implemented.

References

Afzal, N. (2019) A Study on Vocabulary-Learning Problems Encountered by BA English Majors at the University Level of Education file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/6%20(1).pdf

Alam, N. (2021). The importance of parent's literacy understanding towards children reading habits. Library Philosophy and Practice (ejournal), https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348186348_The_Importance_of_Parent%27s_Literacy_Understanding_Towards_Children_Reading_Habits

Al-Sofi, B. (2020). Students' perceptions of the effectiveness of using Smartphone applications in enhancing vocabulary acquisition. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Bakr-Al-Sofi/publication/351497017_Students'_Perceptions_of_the_Effectiveness_of_Using_Smartphone_Applications_in_Enhancing_Vocabulary_Acquisition/links/609af88a299bf1ad8d950d32/Students-Perceptions-of-the-Effectiveness-of-Using-Smartphone-Applications-in-Enhancing-Vocabulary-Acquisition.pdf

Amadi D. (2019) Definition of Vocabulary https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332859814_Vocabulary_Development

Arden, P. (2022). Readability of selected Literary Texts in English and level of mastery in comprehension skills. https://scimatic.org/show_manuscript/400

Bartlett F., (1932) Schema Theory. Understanding human perception by human-made illusions. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0959354313500166#:~:text=The%20concept%20of%20schema%20was,relation%20betwe en%20organism%20and%20environment.>

Bates E., Dale P., Thal D., (2017) Individual differences and their implications for theories of language development https://www.researchgate.net/publication/239064682_Individual_differences_and_their_implications_for_theories_of_language_dev elopment

Beck & McKeown (2019) Read Aloud Strategies. Reading to Learn from the Start <https://minds.wisconsin.edu/handle/1793/80334>

Dakhi, S. (2019). The principles and the teaching of English vocabulary: A review https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3378646

Ghalebi, R. (2020). Vocabulary learning strategies: A comparative study of EFL learners <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23311908.2020.1824306>

Hanna K T. (2023) What is an action plan? <https://www.techtargt.com/whatis/definition/action-plan>

Karami, A. (2019). Audio-Visual Materials (Videos), as an incidental vocabulary learning strategy, in second/foreign Language learners' vocabulary development: Journal on English Language Teaching. https://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&as_vis=1&q=Karami%2C+A.+%282019%29+that+vocabulary+teachi ng+and+learning+has+always+been+a+difficult+task+for+both+language+teachers+and+learners&btnG=

Lawrence, J. (2021). Reading comprehension and academic vocabulary: Exploring relations of Item features and reading proficiency <https://ila.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/rrq.434>

Laubscher, E. (2020). Core vocabulary lists for young children and considerations for early language development: a narrative review <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/07434618.2020.1737964>

LervAag, Cain, & Silva., (2018) Contribution of Vocabulary Knowledge to Reading Comprehension Among Chinese Students: A Meta-Analysis. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.525369/full>

McKeown, M. (2019) Effective Vocabulary Instruction Fosters Knowing Words, Using Words, and Understanding How Words Work. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8753997/>

Moody, S., Xueyan H. & Zhihong X. (2018) Vocabulary Instruction: A Critical Analysis of Theories, Research, and Practice. <https://mdpires.com/bookfiles/book/1252/Vocabulary>. <https://www.thoughtco.com/vocabulary-definition-1692597>

Pickering, H., Peters, J. & Crewther, S. (2022). A role for visual memory in vocabulary development: A systematic review and meta-analysis: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11065-022-09561-4>

Reichardt, C.S. (2019) Quasi-Experimentation: A Guide to Design and Analysis. The Guilford Press <https://quantifyinghealth.com/one-group-pretest-posttest-design/>

Reading Horizons (2023) Teaching Vocabulary, RH Accelerate Online Resources info@readinghorizons.com

Samuelson, L. (2021) Toward a Precision Science of Word Learning <https://srcd.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/cdep.12408>

Sanchez, A. (2020). Expanding English Vocabulary Knowledge through Reading: Insights from Eye-tracking Studies. Sage Journals <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0033688220906904>

Skinner B.F. (1989) Skinner's ABCs of Behaviorism <https://www.verywellmind.com/b-f-skinner-biography-1904-1990-2795543#:~:text=ABCs%20of%20Behaviorism-,B.%20F.,ABCs%20of%20behaviorism%20were%20developed.>

Summer Big Brother Module (2020) Early Grade SBB Module, Conrado and Ladislawa Foundation (CLAFI) Saranggani Division

Susanto, A. (2019). Vocabulary learning strategies, vocabulary skills, and integrative motivation levels among university students <https://www.ijeat.org/wp-content/uploads/papers/v8i5C/E10460585C19.pdf>

Syafrizal, S., & Haerudin H., (2018). The implementation of vocabulary building strategy in teaching English vocabulary to young learners. Journal of English Language Teaching <https://ejournal.undikma.ac.id/index.php/joelt/article/view/2296>

Vygotsky L. (1978). Vygotskian Vocabulary Development Theory [https://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar?q=Vygotsky+L.+\(1978\).+Vygotskian+Vocabulary+Development+Theory&hl=en&as_sdt=0&as_vis=1&oi=scholar](https://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar?q=Vygotsky+L.+(1978).+Vygotskian+Vocabulary+Development+Theory&hl=en&as_sdt=0&as_vis=1&oi=scholar)

Vygotski L. & Piaget J., (1950) Cognitivism Theory [https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=r7XOEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA99&dq=Vygotsky+L.+\(1950\)+Cognitivism+Theory+1950&ots=U7RmJofyAz&sig=sW1G3gQ4XIMVf4d5V_1V7iekJk8&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false](https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=r7XOEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA99&dq=Vygotsky+L.+(1950)+Cognitivism+Theory+1950&ots=U7RmJofyAz&sig=sW1G3gQ4XIMVf4d5V_1V7iekJk8&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false)

Writer, L., (2020). Why Read? The importance of instilling a love of reading early. <https://www.rochester.edu/warner/horizons/2019/10/31/why-read-the-importance-of-instilling-a-love-of-reading-early/>

Zarfsaz, E. & Yeganehpour, P. (2021). The Impact of Different Context Levels on Vocabulary Learning and Retention. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1309657.pdf>

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